

Extension of Quantum Error Correction

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Abstract—A Working Principle of Quantum Error Correction follows encoding, redundancy, error detection, correction and also includes no cloning theorem but our theory concludes with excluding no cloning theorem because of no chances of cloning quantum states due to introducing concealed error at feedback control within quantum control system framework as cited at[1] .

Index Terms—Quantum Information, Decoherence, Quantum Error Correction

I. INTRODUCTION

Quantum error Correction is a technique developed in the field of quantum computing to secure the fragile quantum information and prevent it from occurring error due to decoherence and noises. Moreover when quantum system are inherently noisy due to decoherence i.e, qubits losing super position of quantum states over time due to bad interaction with environment which includes entangling gates that causes gate error due to faulty quantum operations.

II. ADVANTAGES OVER FAULTY OPERATIONS

As we discussed in our previous research paper cited at [1] i.e, within the framework of quantum control systems, feedback control which conceals error and eventually this error will be computed by quantum error correction moreover, no cloning theorem is not mandatory during computing quantum error correction because chances of cloning of quantum state is zero due to concealed error. Instead of computing error within feedback control, adjustment means encrypting error with 1 0, 1 1 or 0 1, 0 0 i.e, encrypting with qubits will conceals error at feedback control which is also a part of quantum control system frame work. Moreover, Mika Hirvensalo et. al, [2] stated that maximum number of computational steps that can be accomplished without losing coherence for various quantum systems.

III. CONCLUSION

We Conclude that Concealed error responses only to decoherence and not noises moreover imperfect operations will be rectified based on functionality of feedback control.

REFERENCES

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